

HOW TO FOSTER CREATIVITY AT UZBEK SCHOOLS?

Khakimova Nargiz Khayrilloyevna

The Teacher of History and Philology Department

Asia International University.

Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Email: xnargiz92@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This article discusses the ideas regarding the topic of nurturing creativity at Uzbek schools and the ways of implementing it. Different ideas can be realized in schools such as innovative approaches to teaching and professional outdoor activities that can help boost creativity in students.*

Keywords: *creativity, motivation, innovation, creative abilities.*

КАК РАЗВИВАТЬ ТВОРЧЕСТВО В УЗБЕКСКИХ ШКОЛАХ?

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются идеи, касающиеся темы воспитания творчества в узбекских школах и пути ее реализации. В школах могут быть реализованы различные идеи, такие как инновационные подходы к обучению и профессиональные мероприятия на свежем воздухе, которые могут помочь повысить творческие способности учащихся.*

Ключевые слова: *креативность, мотивация, новаторство, творческие способности.*

Introduction

Creativity can be regarded as a social phenomenon since it is a part of society. Every person is unique with hidden talents and unexplored depth. Everyone possesses creative abilities.

However, not everyone has the power or confidence to bring it into existence.

Unfortunately, not everyone is taught to be creative at all. Schools here play an important role when it comes to nurturing the personality of children. Moreover, it is crucial when a school can detect the creative abilities of a child from a very early age. Otherwise, it stays undetected.

Lack of creativity in the lessons, the lessons that do not promote creativity are the problems that do not allow the students to realize their creative abilities. As a result, they grow up into a dull and stressed adult with as many problems and no creative problem-solving abilities. *How to foster creativity at schools so students start realizing their creative abilities?*

Nowadays, the term "Creativity" is becoming a trend and it is progressing in every sphere of our life. In Education, it has visible advantages for both teachers and students. According to the survey conducted by Canva Team in 2020, 66% of educators agreed that creativity allows students to express themselves in the classroom more freely and without any complexity. (*Canva Team, 2020*) For instance, the creative classroom can transform the understanding of a student toward study. It also makes the learning process full of fun and excitement and improves communication and problem-solving skills. What is more important, it gives the learners unforgettable emotions for their whole life. (*Role and Importance of Creativity in the Classroom | Kasiga School, n.d.*)

For teachers, it also has a very great influence. They will get job satisfaction whenever their students perform better skills inside and outside of the classroom.

What could be better than to see your student succeed?

So, here is the question: How to foster creativity at Uzbek schools so the students will be free enough to expressions and communicate?

Methods

School curriculum should be redesigned according to creative standards. First, an innovative environment should be created within the classroom so that every student will be able to propose changes if it is needed or bring examples of innovations. By working in an innovative learning environment where education and learning are coordinated and reflections and inquiries are shared, the communities involved lead to a more robust and continuously improving hands-on community. In addition, innovative approaches during lessons can be effective in stepping ahead toward our goal. New teaching methods and innovative lessons can maintain the innovative learning environment better.

In other words, if we include games or role-plays in the lesson process then it can follow the boost of positive interest from students' side. Games have a very deep influence on the student's behavior. It means more motivation, higher self-esteem, better memory, language development, and increased learning desire. (*Sager, 2021*) Therefore, it is crucial to include these elements in the lessons. The creative process of teaching is a series of thoughts and actions that lead to innovative and adaptive production, in other words, to an innovative lesson. (*Lubart, 2001*) To organize a creative environment for students, Uzbek schools can provide the educators and the students with facilities, such as tools, stationery, a piece of paper or so, to be involved in the creative process in the classroom. If there is a chance for children to express themselves, they will probably be ready to turn their most crazy and unbelievable ideas into reality. In addition, positive feedback, better marks, rewards, or appreciation in front of the class may have a very motivating effect on the students. Thinking about how to nurture creativity in children inevitably brings together parents, teachers, and scientists from different disciplines.

Children's belief in the existence of creativity helps to "embody" it by paying more attention to all cases of potential creative value. (*Glăveanu, 2011*) A teacher is only responsible for a creative lesson. If parents alongside a teacher start bringing up creativity in a child's life, then probably the child will end up discovering new features of his or her personality and will not be lost in the future.

The idea of organizing creativity sections will make sense. If we talk about afterschool sections, it would be great if there were theatre club sections at schools in our country. Instead of sitting in the classroom and trying to memorize the subject of the text, we can give the students a chance to discover a talent that they do not even know they have. One American teacher found very positive benefits from the Drama sections organized in her school. She concludes that the benefits of this shift, the increased comfort of public speaking and public appearance, were also visible in the classroom as performances were significantly improved and group work became easier. And freshmen always found someone to greet them. (*The Many Benefits of a Middle School Drama Club, n.d.*) So, we can see here that this novelty makes the learning process more open and adaptable for every type of personality that the students have. Even introverts can be able to participate and succeed.

Within the classroom, we must inspire students with real, live examples. For instance, we can invite someone who achieved success in the creative sphere or any other sphere and present him or her to the class. Then this person would share the experience of his success and explain the ways of how to do it. After that, students would probably work with this person by doing the work that he or she does: drawing a picture with an artist or imaginary doing surgery with a surgeon.

Therefore, there is evidence that inspiration or motivation is a very powerful element of children's development as it is the driving force for taking action and completing a given task. It is important for parents and teachers to understand the level of motivation of young people and to guide them in their areas of interest accordingly. (*Importance of Motivation in Early Childhood Education - Ruby Park Public School, n.d.*)

One more idea that would be successful is a live outdoor experience. For instance, the students can go to museums, theatres, galleries, or festivals. (If there is any in that region) Nevertheless, more grandiose is a professional experience, where the students would spend their time experiencing any profession such as a doctor, firefighter, or any other. A world-famous Kidzania can be a great example of this. It is a family entertainment center, designed as a recreation for children in a real city, with buildings, shops, theaters, as well as vehicles and pedestrians traveling down the street. It involves realistic role-playing fun and learning that motivates children to explore over 100 exciting professions on their own within the imaginary city. (*KidZania - Get Ready for a Better World®*, n.d.) How effective it would work out if the students wore the skin of the representatives of different professions? It can push them to understand what they want from their life from that age and what profession they would like to take in the future.

To establish an innovative environment, a school curriculum should be optimized. In addition, technologically equipped classes can open broader possibilities for the learning process.

Of course, it is impossible to be achieved without an experienced teacher in the classroom. Curriculum should be stressed in this situation. It should include interactive games, role-plays and other kind of activities. At that time, we can approach innovatively to the lessons.

As for theatre clubs, the school administration can have an agreement with a theatre close to them and organize theatre clubs in the theatre. It will have much effect if the students will feel the atmosphere physically. To reach the outdoor live experience, we can come up with two possible solutions for implementation. The first is to find a company primarily for this kind of purpose. Schools can contact this company if they want to organize field trips for children. They will have different choices such as visiting a dentist or a firefighter and they can spend their time observing their work and asking questions. I think it will have a positive impact on both children and the professionals as well. For example, the students will not feel fear in front of a dentist after that.

The second is to sign a contract with the original Kidzania and take the initiative in opening one of their branches here in Uzbekistan.

The strengths of these ideas are their availability and feasibility. Here George Bernard Shaw said, "Imagination is the beginning of creation. You imagine what you desire, you will what you imagine, and at last, you create what you will." It is indeed true. Imagination is a foundation for creativity. Everyone has creative abilities but not everyone has the chance to understand and accept that. More importantly, it is crucial to detect creative abilities when it is still early. "Every child is an artist, the problem is staying an artist when you grow up," said Pablo Picasso. The main

purpose of the teachers is to bring out this creativity in the child and nourish it so it will grow and flourish. We need creativity in every phase of our lives, let it be professional or personal. By fostering creativity at schools, we can succeed in our aim. Then schools become some sort of creative inspiration and turn to become an attachment for each student.

Conclusion

On a final note, we can assume that fostering creativity at schools is a very vital case as it may be the main reason for students' success in the future. When a student is accustomed to working creatively in any situation, he or she will not be given a chance to fail. With a better curriculum, experienced teachers, and innovative solutions it can be achieved and implemented.

"There is no doubt that creativity is the most important human resource of all. Without creativity, there would be no progress, and we would be forever repeating the same patterns". - Edward de Bono.

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